

Project RASHealth: Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems

Deliverable 3.1

Technical internal report on the effect of PAA exposure on Atlantic salmon parr welfare and growth.

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Background

Atlantic salmon parr tolerance level to peracetic acid (PAA) is unknown.

RASHealth ambition: To document PAA's effect on Atlantic salmon parr health, welfare and growth and, to evaluate two administration methods.

Background

Task 3.1 Determination of the PAA exposure concentration and administration method without effect on Atlantic salmon parr health, welfare or growth.

Aim: To determine the PAA concentration and administration in which no negative consequences are observed in Atlantic salmon parr performance (**SO3**).

Material and Methods

Experimental design: Trial 1.1. 1-hour PAA exposure

Fish: Atlantic salmon parr (± 11 g)

Systems: 9 RAS, fish tank volume 500L

Treatment: 9 concentrations (mg/L PAA): 0.0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2 and 6.4

PAA: 6.6 % Peracetic acid; 23.4 % Hydrogen peroxide; 10% Acetic acid (Aqua Des, Aquatic Chemistry AS, Norway)

Results

Percentage survival (%) of Atlantic salmon parr exposed to different PAA concentrations.

Results

Fish behaviour characterized by swimming activity and appetite.

A) Swimming behaviour during 1 h PAA exposure was assessed using a 1 to 3-point system, where 0 indicates no reaction to PAA and 3 indicates intense swimming activity.

B) Appetite (%) during three days in relation to the control group (0 mg/L). PAA 3.2 and 6.4 mg/L are not shown due to the early termination of these two groups.

Different superscript letters represent statistically significant differences among treatment groups (P-value < 0.05).

Results

Histological assessment of skin health.

Skin health was evaluated using 2 key parameters: A) general appearance and B) surface quality, using a score system of 0 (good) to 3 (poor) condition. Mucous cells density (nr cells/ μm^2) C) acid cells and D) neutral cells.

Different superscript letters represent statistically significant differences among treatment groups (P-value < 0.05).

Results

Representative photographs of A) healthy skin, with defined structures, smooth surface and intact epithelium and B) a compromised skin with rough surface and missing epidermal layer. Note mucous acid cells (in blue) and neutral cells (in purple) in these two photographs.

A.

B.

Results

Histological assessment of gill health.

A) Gill health was assessed by counting the prevalence of pathologies often observed following oxidant treatments in Atlantic salmon, including PAA exposure. Representative photographs of B) healthy gills with well-defined structures, C) epithelial lifting in the secondary lamella (arrows), D) necrotic gills with dead tissue (arrows) and E) aneurysm and hyperplasia of epithelial cells.

Results

Water pH of each fish tank before and 60 min. after PAA administration.
 Δ (delta) -value between pH at 0 min. and pH at 60 min.

Discussion

- In the current study Atlantic salmon parr was exposed twice to 1h PAA (0.0 - 6.4 mg/L).
- The fish survival was 100, 80 and 0%, respectively ≤ 1.6 , 3.2 and 6.4 mg/L PAA.
- Fish swimming behaviour was normal in PAA ≤ 1.6 mg/L, whereas it become erratic with air gasping for PAA ≥ 3.2 mg/L.
- Skin and gill histopathological changes were substantial in PAA ≥ 3.2 mg/L, especially poorer skin condition and gill lamellar necrosis.

Conclusions

- The no-observed-effect concentration of PAA for Atlantic salmon parr to be below 1.6 mg/L thus providing support for its eventual use as a routine water disinfectant.
- Fish mortality and the health status of skin and gill was severely compromised at PAA concentrations equal or higher than 3.2 mg/L, whereas changes in swimming behaviour were pronounced at concentrations equal or higher than 1.6 mg/L.
- Fish swimming activity could provide an early warning to the distress and eventual mortality, that are associated with PAA exposure.

Conclusions

- The strong acidification effect of PAA-based products should be considered on the product toxicity and on the pH reduction of low water alkalinity aquaculture systems.
- The data from this study is relevant for potential application of PAA as a routine RAS loop water disinfectant.
- Further studies should evaluate the health and welfare consequences of a long-term PAA exposure and determine how other environmental parameters in RAS may contribute to its toxicity.
- As commercial PAA products are available in different formulations, including stabilizers which may elicit different physiological responses, the observations reported are specific to the product used in the present study.

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